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Responses of plantroot and soil microbial respiration to seasonal rain events in a mixed-grass prairie under different grazing intensities

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Abstract: Despite heavy study in past decades, responses of the major components of soil respiration (root-derived vs. soil microbe derived) to environmental factors is still not well-understood. This is mainly due to the inaccessibility of major soil organisms for experimental manipulation. Based on data collected in the 2009 growing season, we used a field trenching method for soil respiration partitioning in a mixed-grass rangelands with two different grazing histories. Total soil respiration was modeled as a function of soil temperature, soil water content and leaf area index, while microbial respiration (from trenched plots) was modeled as a function of soil temperature and soil water content. The models explained 62% to 67% of the variations in data. Over 111 days, from May 14 to September 1, 2009, the average fraction of root respiration (out of the total respiration) was estimated to be 54% and 67% under moderate grazing and heavy grazing, respectively. These percentages include root respiration, rhizosphere respiration, and the microbial respiration of decaying plant roots. Both modeled and measured root respiration rates showed higher values during the rapid growth period from May to early July. Root respiration mainly responded to large rain events and was relatively insensitive to temperature pulses. Microbial respiration responded to both the rain and temperature pulses. Respiration cost for leaf production (and presumably also for forage production) tended to be lower under moderate grazing than under heavy grazing. Further study involving multi-year data and alternative models is needed to minimize the underestimation seen in this paper for predicting soil respiration under field conditions.

1 Introduction

Under scenarios of multifactor global climate change, the dynamics of grassland ecosystems is strongly regulated by the coupling of water, carbon and nitrogen flows (Collins et al., 2008; Weng and Luo, 2008). Similar to the situations in other arid and semi-arid ecosystems, precipitation pulses and size class distribution may have strong implications in grasslands (Reynolds et al., 2004). While small rain events may easily trigger microbial activity, large ones capable of infiltrating to deeper soil layers are more valuable for vascular plants. Soil CO₂ evolution is the result of the biological activity of various organisms enclosed within the soil porous medium. Properly partitioning soil respiration between plant-derived (due to plant root growth, nutrient uptake, and associated rhizosphere microbial activities) and soil organic matter decomposition-related portions will not only help in assessing the source and sink strength of the carbon flux, it is also crucial for deciphering mechanisms regulating plant biomass production and nutrient cycling (Raich and Tufekcioglu, 2000). In particular, in-depth knowledge is lacking regarding the differential responses of plant-derived and soil organic matter (SOM)-derived soil respiration to varying rain events in grasslands (Huxman et al., 2004), despite recent progress (Byrne and Kiely, 2006; Jia et al., 2006; Skinner, 2011).

One biggest challenge for soil respiration partitioning is the “inaccessibility of the organisms of interest within the soil” (Skinner, 2011). As a result the quest for deeper mechanisms is almost always plagued with

the inevitable disturbance and disruption to the integrity of the soil biological system (Kuzyakov, 2006). Soil trenching, despite its drawback of lumping root respiration with microbial contributions, has been shown to be useful for respiration partitioning under field conditions (Baggs, 2006; Bond-Lamberty et al., 2011). Great attention has been devoted to the forest ecosystems (Ewel et al., 1987; Bowden et al., 1993; Epron et al., 1999; Lee et al., 2003; Yi, et al., 2007), but application in grasslands is limited.

In this study we use the field trenching method to partition soil respiration into plant-derived (referred to as "root respiration" for simplicity) and microbial-derived contribution within two long-term grazing pastures in the mixed-grass prairie. The limitation of our chamber method prevented us from addressing the total ecosystem respiration, as has frequently been considered in the power-based studies of CO₂ flux. But we will address the issue of the cost of root respiration for forage production in grasslands. In particular, we wanted to know the underlying mechanisms associated with the degradation of grasslands due to long-term heavy use. It has been shown by Patton et al. (2007) that long-term moderate use (grazing by yearling beef cattle) led to optimal forage production, when compared with long-term heavy use. We hoped to see if the reduction of forage growth due to long-term heavy use was also accompanied with a proportional reduction in root respiration. This is an interesting issue because cattle grazing directly affects the leafy tissue of plants, but it affects roots indirectly. Finally, we will also compare the potential differential responses of root and microbial respiration to seasonal rain events and temperature fluctuations.

2 Materials and Methods

The work was conducted on mixed-grass prairie rangeland near Streeter, ND, USA, within a long-term grazing intensity study site as described by Patton et al. (2007). This long-term experiment was initiated in 1988, but the study site has not been plowed in the past 50 years. So, the vegetation is close to that of the native prairie (Fig. 1). The site has an annual precipitation of 454 mm, with 72% occurring from May to September. The average January and August mean air temperatures are -16 °C and 20 °C. The soils are rocky (but see Fig. 1 for evidence of past plowing). Dominant grasses include Kentucky bluegrass (*Poa pratensis* L.), western wheatgrass (*Pascopyrum smithii* [Rydb.] A. Löve), green needlegrass (*Nassella viridula* [Trin.] Barkworth) and smooth brome (*Bromus inermis* Leyss.); dominant forbs include western yarrow (*Achillea millefolium* L.), white sage (*Artemisia ludoviciana* Nutt.) and Stiff goldenrod (*Oligoneuron rigidum* [L.] Small var. *humile* [Porter] Nesom); and the dominant shrub is western snowberry (*Symphoricarpos occidentalis* Hook.). Most grasses have C₃ photosynthesis and attain maximum growth in June, while the rapid growth of dominant forbs occurs in July to August.

One moderately grazed (stocking rate of 2.7 animal unit month (AUM) ha⁻¹) and one heavily grazed (6.9AUM ha⁻¹) pasture was selected for studying carbon flux (Fig. 1). Under moderate grazing (MG), about 50% of the forage in an "average year" was utilized by cattle; under heavy grazing (HG), the forage utilization rate is 80%. Within each pasture, one 15 m × 15 m plot located on an upland area was fenced in 2005 to prevent disturbance by cattle. Eight 1 m × 1 m plots were identified within each plot area. Four of the eight sub-plots (1 m × 1 m) were used for drought treatment and four others as control. This study only concerns the four control sub-plots. Two of them were randomly selected as trenched sub-plots, in which the soil block was

physically isolated by digging to 1 m deep around the edges and lined with two layers of 0.25 mm thick plastic sheet, following Ewel et al. (1987) and Lee et al. (2003). This was to prevent roots from growing into the trenched plot area. Plants in the trenched plot area were frequently clipped to prevent growth of new roots. The other two sub-plots were not trenched and maintained in natural condition. This is part of the multi-year (2009-2013) research project relating grassland soil respiration to multiple biotic and abiotic factors. But in this preliminary report we only consider data collected in the 2009 growing season.

Fig. 1 Two pastures (each about 12.8 ha), one under moderate season-long grazing since 1989 (to the right of fence) and one under heavy grazing (left), as seen in August, 2006. This area has not been plowed in the past 50-60 years (note the pile of rocks in the moderately grazed pasture). Thus the vegetation is close to that of native prairie. Photo credit: Rick Bohn.

In each of 1 m × 1 m plot area, one metal access tube was inserted 1.4 to 1.6 m deep in order to guide the neutron probe for soil water measurement, which was conducted weekly or biweekly using a Troxler Depth Moisture Gauge Model 4301 (Research Triangle Park, NC, USA) during the growing season. Also, one 12 cm deep PVC pipe was inserted permanently inside each plot area. The width of the PVC pipe was chosen to match the size of the LI-COR 6400-09 respiration chamber (LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, Nebraska USA). Soil respiration rate was measured once a week using the LI-COR 6400 Portable Photosynthesis System with the 6400-09 respiration chamber in the morning (6:30-8:00 AM local time) and afternoon (2:30 to 3:30 PM). Soil temperatures at 2.5 cm and 10 cm depths were measured by a set of T-type thermocouples within trenched and control plots in both pastures. Data was recorded at 2 hour intervals using a CR3000 data logger and a CR10X data logger in conjunction with an AM 416 relay Multiplexer (Campbell Scientific, Inc., Logan, Utah, USA).

Soil water content at 2.5 and 10 cm depths was measured using a set of ECHO probes (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA). But due to sensor malfunction, we had to rely on a model estimate of soil water content. In particular, soil water content at 7.6 cm depth from the plot of MG was adapted from the modeling results of Dong et al. (2010). The same model was applied to simulate soil water dynamics for the plot under

HG during the growing season in 2009. The model of Dong et al. (2010) was essentially an extended form of the soil water infiltration-redistribution model written by Warrick (2003). The main components added include (a) plant root water uptake, its response to varying soil water potentials, and the compensated water uptake under drought stress; and (b) transpiration and soil evaporation. The model, driven by hourly precipitation, air temperature, relative humidity and leaf area index, simulates seasonal soil water dynamics with a spatial increment of 2.5 cm of soil depth and time increment of 2 min.

To stop new roots from growing in the trenched plots, glyphosate was applied twice (by brushing the green leaf surface with minimum of the chemical) in 2006 summer. In 2007, the herbicide was applied once in spring. Later on, new root growth within the trenched plot area was discouraged by frequent clipping. Leaf area index (LAI) was measured twice a month using a ceptometer (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA) from plots of MG and HG and the data were interpolated to obtain the daily values.

Measured respiration rate from the trenched plots (R_H) was considered as a function of soil temperature (T , averaged values of temperatures measured at 2.5 and 10 cm depths) and soil water content at 7.6 cm depth (θ , from model simulation) using an empirical model (Tang et al. 2006):

$$R_H = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 T} \theta^{\beta_2} \quad (1)$$

where β_0 , β_1 and β_2 are coefficients to be estimated. By a natural log transformation, Eq. (1) can be transformed into a linear equation, $\log(R_H) = \log(\beta_0) + \beta_1 T + \beta_2 \log(\theta)$, for which parameters can be estimated by linear regression. Likewise, the measured respiration from the control plots (R_{Total}) was considered as a function of soil temperature (T), soil water content at 7.6 cm depth (θ) and leaf area index (L):

$$R_{Total} = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 T} \theta^{\beta_2} L^{\beta_3} \quad (2)$$

where β_0 , β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are coefficients to be estimated. The regression analysis was conducted using the `lm` function of R (R Development Core Team, 2011). Daily values of microbial respiration (R_H) and total soil respiration (R_{Total}) during the growing season of 2009 were estimated by applying Eqs. (1) and (2) to the daily values of soil temperature, soil water content and leaf area index as described above. Root respiration (R_R) was obtained by subtracting R_H from R_{Total} .

3 Results

Seasonal dynamics of LAI from May 14 to September 1, 2009 are shown in Fig. 2. Leaves in both the MG and HG plots grew rapidly from Mid-May to early July. A heavy clipping on July 9 (in MG plots) and July 11 (HG plots) greatly reduced LAI. The rapid leaf growth prior to the heavy clipping corresponds with several rain events in mid-June and the general trend of increasing temperature starting from early June (Fig. 3a). Soil temperature under HG tended higher in warm days, and lower in cool day, than that under MG. Following a dry period of about a month (from mid-July to mid-August), a heavy rain of 42 mm occurred during Aug. 14-16. The simulated soil water contents at 7.6 cm depth in both the HG and MG plots responded sensitively to this heavy rain event (Fig. 3b). Soil water at this depth also responded to several major rain events in mid-June to

mid-July. Soil water content in the HG plots tended higher than that in the MG plots, as seen both in measured and simulated soil water contents. The model underestimated soil water content on several days in the HG plots (June 9, June, 15, and July 15); it overestimated soil water during the drought period of early to mid-August (just before the August heavy rain).

Table 1 Fitted parameters of the empirical models for total soil respiration (R_{Total}) in plots of heavy and moderate grazing. The model is $R_{Total} = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 T} \theta^{\beta_2} L^{\beta_3}$, where T is soil temperature ($^{\circ}C$), θ is volumetric soil water content and L is leaf area index.

Grazing intensity	Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	p value	R ²
Moderate	$\log(\beta_0)$	2.466	0.525	4.70	0.0001	0.62
	β_1	0.018	0.012	1.575	0.129	
	β_2	1.251	0.339	3.694	0.001	
	β_3	0.784	0.241	3.261	0.004	
Heavy	$\log(\beta_0)$	2.759	0.392	7.037	<0.0001	0.63
	β_1	0.027	0.009	2.835	0.01	
	β_2	1.543	0.281	5.491	<0.0001	
	β_3	0.163	0.113	1.443	0.163	

Table 2 Fitted parameters of the empirical models for microbial respiration (R_H) in plots of heavy and moderate grazing. The model is $R_H = \beta_0 e^{\beta_1 T} \theta^{\beta_2}$, where T is soil temperature ($^{\circ}C$) and θ is volumetric soil water content.

Grazing intensity	Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	p value	R ²
Moderate	$\log(\beta_0)$	1.620	0.484	3.345	0.002	0.67
	β_1	0.057	0.006	9.433	<0.0001	
	β_2	1.571	0.381	4.121	0.0001	
Heavy	$\log(\beta_0)$	1.685	0.544	3.098	0.003	0.66
	β_1	0.073	0.008	9.344	<0.0001	
	β_2	2.341	0.498	4.698	<0.0001	

The models for R_{Total} and R_H explained 62% and 66% of the variations in the measured values (Tables 1-2). As shown in Fig. 4, the models capture general trend of the measured data in early at 8AM. However, there are several cases of underestimation by the models. This underestimation is also seen in the comparison between model predictions and measurements at 3 PM (Fig. 5). The recovered root respiration (R_R) and microbial respiration (R_H), expressed as amount of CO₂ respired per day are shown in Fig. 6. From June 8 to July 18, estimated R_R was higher than R_H , before and after that period, the reverse trend was predicted (Fig. 6b). The behavior of R_R and R_H one week before the mid-August heavy rain deserves mentioning. The predicted R_R continued to decrease despite the rain event of 5.6 mm occurring on Aug. 9 (Fig. 6a), also despite the steady

increase of soil temperature from Aug. 9 (20.5 °C) to Aug. 13 (25.4 °C). On the other hand, the predicted R_H increased from Aug. 9 to 13, which is verified by the increase in the measured microbial respiration for both HG and MG plots at 3 PM on Aug. 12 (see Fig. 5c). In general, the predicted R_H responded to both soil temperature and rain pulses (large or small) while R_R mainly responded to large rain events (> than 10 mm), but was not sensitive to surface soil temperature. Finally, the predicted R_H responded to the mid-August heavy rain more dramatically than did the predicted R_R (Fig. 6). On the average, soil microbial respiration under heavy grazing was about 36% lower than that under moderate grazing, as seen from the seasonal dynamics predicted by models.

Fig. 2 Seasonal trends in leaf area index of the experimental plots. Plots were fenced in 2005 and the vegetation was clipped manually to match that remaining in the pasture under cattle grazing. Leaf area index was measured biweekly using a ceptometer and interpolated to daily values from May to September, 2009. Note the heavy clippings on Jul. 9 and 11. Data points prior to the clippings were fitted to a sigmoidal growth curve (Gardner et al., 1985); the points following the clippings were interpolated using a rational polynomial according to Hanna and Sandall (1995).

Fig. 3 (a) Daily precipitation and daily average soil temperature (the average of readings at 10 cm and 2.5 cm depths) for plots of moderate (solid) and heavy (dotted) grazing. (b) A comparison of measured (symbols) and simulated (lines) soil water content at the depth of 7.6 cm in plots of moderate and heavy grazing in the growing season of 2009.

Averaging over the 111 days from May to September, the fraction of root respiration in the MG and HG plots was 54% and 67%, respectively (Fig. 7). The values for the HG plots did not exhibit much seasonality, while the root contribution increased from May 29 to July 5 on the MG plots, accompanying the period with high LAI (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 4 (a) Same as that of Fig. 3 (a). (b) A comparison of model simulated (lines) and measured total soil respiration rate (from control plots) at 8 AM from May 14 to Sep. 1, 2009 for plots with moderate (solid lines and solid circles) and heavy (dotted line and open circles) grazing history. (c) Same as (b) but with the trenched plots (for microbial respiration).

4 Discussion

The seasonal averaged fractions of root respiration of our study are higher than values obtained in several other grasslands. Skinner (2011) estimated that root respiration under orchardgrass and white clover pasture in Pennsylvania averaged 50% from July to September but was 40% in May. Byrne and Kiely (2006) estimated that the root respiration accounted for 50% of total soil respiration under an intensively managed perennial ryegrass plantation in southern Ireland. Under greenhouse condition, Jia et al (2006) estimated that root respiration fraction was 30% to 37% for *Leymus chinensis* populations. To be consistent with the terminology of Kuzyakov (2006), the root respiration (R_R) in our work actually consisted of three components: (a) actual root respiration; (b) rhizomicrobial respiration; and (c) microbial respiration for decomposing dead roots. The first two components (root respiration itself and rhizomicrobial respiration) are difficult to discern under field conditions, and many researchers, such as Skinner (2011), simply used the term rhizosphere respiration to represent them. In our study, natural plots continued to have new roots growing during the growing seasons,

but the trenched plots didn't. Following one growing season, the new roots in the natural plots may deposit as litter and started to decompose. Research conducted at this same site addresses the rate of decomposition of different types of belowground plant biomass (fine roots, coarse roots and rhizomes) over three years from 2006 to 2009 (X. Dong, unpublished). Future work is needed to quantify the decomposition of dead roots over multiple years so that our estimated R_R will only include root and rhizomicrobial respiration.

Fig. 5 (a) Same as that of Fig. 3 (a). (b) A comparison of model simulated (lines) and measured total soil respiration rate (from control plots) at 3 PM from May 14 to Sep. 1, 2009 for plots with moderate (solid lines and solid circles) and heavy (dotted line and open circles) grazing history. (c) Same as (b) but with the trenched plots (for microbial respiration).

Table 3. Accumulated root respiration and leaf production in plots of moderate and heavy grazing during the 53 days from May 14 to Jul. 6, 2009.

Grazing intensity	Leave mass [§] (kg/ha)	Root respiration (kg CO ₂ /ha)	Root respiration cost for leaf production (kg CO ₂ respired / kg leaves)
Moderate	1485	4816	3.2
Heavy	416	3784	9.1

[§] Assuming a typical specific leaf area of 69 g m⁻² for grasses of the mixed-grass prairie (Dong et al., 2011).

Fig. 6 (a) Same as that of Fig. 3 (a). (b) Dynamics of daily root respiration (estimated root-free respiration subtracted from total soil respiration) for plots of heavy and moderate grazing from May 14 to Sep. 1, 2009. (c) Same as in (b) but for microbial respiration.

Fig. 7 Fraction of root respiration (out of total respiration) derived from root and microbial respiration rates of Fig. 6.

The model-predicted daily rates of root respiration for both HG and MG plots (Fig. 6b) allowed us to estimate the root respiration cost for leaf production during the most rapid period of leaf growth from May 14 to Jul. 6, 2009 (as seen in Fig. 2). Using a typical specific leaf area of 69 g m^{-2} for grasses of the mixed-grass prairie (Dong et al., 2011), we estimated (see Table 3) that it was three times more expensive, in terms of root respiration cost, to produce leaves in the HG plots than in the MG plots. This is because the heavy reduction of leaf growth due to long-term heavy use was accompanied with only a moderate reduction in accumulated root respiration during the 53 days of rapid growth from May 14 to July 6, 2009. In other words, respiration efficiency under HG was lower than that under MG. Dong et al. (2012) showed that the longer-term HG in this same grassland had led to a significant reduction in the below-ground rhizomes of the prairie plants. Considering the fact that some dominant plants (such as Kentucky bluegrass and smooth brome) are strongly rhizomatous, one ecophysiological mechanism underlying the long-term heavy use-related grassland

degradation is the dramatic reduction of the below-ground vegetative propagules (bud bank) through altered biomass allocation due to over grazing. This has implications for further studies linking root respiration to plant demography.

The predicted result that root respiration under HG started out higher than under MG (from May 14 to 29; see Fig. 6b) may partly due to the higher soil water contents under HG (see Fig. 3b). But we don't have measured respiration data during that period to verify this. It is interesting to see that R_H responded to the mid-August heavy rain more dramatically than did R_R (Fig. 6b, c), but we don't have data to verify this either. The contrasts between R_H and R_R in their responses to rain events (see Fig. 6) seem compatible with the general features of soil SOM-related microbes (harboring in the micro soil pores) vs. plant roots (residing in large soil pores), with the former being more resistant to drought stress. This may partly explain both the model-predicted and measured results of soil respiration one week before the mid-August heavy rain (see Fig. 6b, c): The daily rates of R_R continued to decrease but the rates of R_H increased, accompanying the increase of soil temperature. The predicted higher R_R in HG than in MG from mid-July to mid-August (Fig. 6b) may be related to the rapid growth of forbs, which occur later (July to August) than grasses (June) in this rangeland, because grazing animals primarily consume grasses but not forbs (Engels, 2002). Further study using multi-year data and adopting alternative (competing) models for R_H and R_R are needed in order to minimize the underestimation of measured soil respiration rates.

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References

1. Baggs, E. M. 2006. Partitioning the components of soil respiration: a research challenge. *Plant Soil*, 284, DOI 10.1007/s11104-006-0047-7
2. Bond-Lamberty, B., Bronson, D., Bladyka, E., Gower, S. T. 2011. A comparison of trenched plot techniques for partitioning soil respiration. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 43, 2108–2114
3. Bowden, R. D., Nadelhoffer, K. J., Boone, R. D., Melillo, J. M., Garrison, J. B. 1993. Contributions of aboveground litter, belowground litter, and root respiration to total soil respiration in a temperate mixed hardwood forest. *Can. J. Forest Res.* 23:1402–1407
4. Byrne, K. A., Kiely, G. 2006. Partitioning of respiration in an intensively managed grassland. *Plant Soil*, 282: 281–289
5. Collins, S. L., Sinsabaugh, R. L., Crenshaw, C., Green, L., Porras-Alfaro, A., Stursova, M., Zeglin, L. H. 2008. Pulse dynamics and microbial processes in aridland ecosystems. *J. Ecol.* 96:413–420
6. Dong, X., Patton, B. D., Nyren, A. C., Nyren, P. E. and Prunty, L. D. 2010. Quantifying root water extraction by range plants through soil water modeling. *Plant Soil*, 335: 181–198
7. Dong, X., Patton, B., Nyren, P., Limb, R., Cihacek, L., Kirby, D., Deckard, E. 2011. Leaf-water relations of a native and an introduced grass species in the mixed-grass prairie under cattle grazing. *Appl. Ecol. Environ. Res.* 9:311–331

8. Dong, X., Cheng, F.-C., Wang, D.-J., Wang, G.-J., Patton, B. D., Nyren, P. E. 2012. Mixed-grass rhizome biomass is influenced by cattle grazing intensity. *Grass Forage Sci*, 68: 199–204
9. Engels, C. L. 2002. The Effect of Grazing Intensity on Rangeland Hydrology. M. S. Thesis, Department of Agricultural Engineering, North Dakota State University, Fargo, ND, USA.
10. Epron, D., Farque, L., Lucot, E., Badot, P.-M. 1999. Soil CO₂ efflux in a beech forest: the contribution of root respiration. *Ann. For. Sci*, 56: 289–295
11. Ewel, K. C., Cropper, Jr., W. P., Gholz, H. L. 1987. Soil CO₂ evolution in Florida slash pine plantations. II. Importance of root respiration. *Can. J. For. Res*, 17:330–333
12. Gardner, F. P., Pearce, R.B., Mitchell, R. L. 1985. *Physiology of Crop Plants*. Iowa State University, Ames.
13. Hanna, O. T., Sandall, O. C. 1995. *Computational Methods in Chemical Engineering*. Prentice Hall International Series in the Physical and Chemical Engineering Sciences, Prentice Hall PTR, Upper Saddle River.
14. Huxman, T. E., Snyder, K. A., Tissue, D., Leffer, A. J., Ogle, K., Pockman, W. T., Sandquist, D. R., Potts, D. L., Schwinning, S. 2004. Precipitation pulses and carbon fluxes in semiarid and arid ecosystems. *Oecologia*, 141: 254–268
15. Jia, B., Zhou, G., Wang, F., Wang, Y., Yuan, W. and Zhou, L. 2006. Partitioning root and microbial contributions to soil respiration in *Leymus chinensis* populations. *Soil Biol. Biochem*, 38:653–660
16. Kuzyakov, Y., 2006. Sources of CO₂ efflux from soil and review of partitioning methods. *Soil Biol. Biochem*, 38: 425–448
17. Lee, M., Nakane, K., Nakatsubo, T., Koizumi, H. 2003. Seasonal changes in the contribution of root respiration to total soil respiration in a cool temperate deciduous forest. *Plant Soil*, 255: 311–318
18. Patton, B. D., Dong, X., Nyren, P. E., Nyren, A. 2007. Effects of grazing intensity, precipitation, and temperature on forage production. *Rangeland Ecol. Manage*, 60:656–665
19. R Development Core Team, 2011. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. ISBN 3-900051-07-0, URL <http://www.R-project.org/>
20. Raich, J. W., Tufekcioglu, A. 2000. Vegetation and soil respiration: correlation and controls. *Biogeochemistry*, 48: 71–90
21. Reynolds, J., Kemp, P., Ogle, K., Fernandez, R. M. 2004. Modifying the 'pulse reserve' paradigm for deserts of North America: Precipitation pulses, soil water and plant responses. *Oecologia*, 141: 194–210
22. Skinner, R. H. 2011. Quantifying rhizosphere respiration for two cool-season perennial forages. *Crop Sci*, 51: 2904–2910
23. Tang, X.-L., Zhou, G.-Y., Liu, S.-G., Zhang, D.-Q., Liu, S.-Z., Li, J., Zhou, C.-Y. 2006. Dependence of soil respiration on soil temperature and soil moisture in successional forests in southern china. *J. Integr. Plant Biol*, 48: 654–663
24. Warrick, A. W. 2003. *Soil Water Dynamics*, Oxford University, New York.
25. Weng, E., Luo, Y. 2008. Soil hydrological properties regulate grassland ecosystem responses to multifactor global change: A modeling analysis. *J. Geophys. Res.* 113, doi:10.1029/2007JG000539
26. Yi, Z., Fu, S., Yi, W., Zhou, G., Mo, J., Zhang, D., Ding, M., Wang, X., Zhou, L. 2007. Partitioning soil respiration of subtropical forests with different successional stages in south China. *Forest. Ecol. Manage*, 243:178–186